

Full Length Research Paper

Analysis of the Socio-Economic Characteristics of Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS) Credit Beneficiaries in Bauchi State, Nigeria

¹Ibrahim, M. T., ²Idrisa, Y. L., ^{*3}Garba, A. and ⁴Murtala, N.

¹Central Bank of Nigeria, Minna Branch, Niger State, Nigeria.

²Department of Agriculture Extension, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

³Department of Agricultural Extension and Management, Binyaminu Usman Polytechnic, Hadejia, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author E-mail: adogarbak@gmail.com

Received 2 June 2019; Accepted 25 June, 2019

The study analyzed the socioeconomic characteristics of beneficiaries of credit under the Agricultural credit guarantee scheme in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Four hundred and five (405) respondents were drawn from the 3 zones of the Bauchi State Agricultural Development Programme for this study. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used and duly acknowledged. Results of the study showed that majority (73.8%) of the Agricultural credit guarantee scheme loan beneficiaries were males and Married (76.5%), Age range of 36-55 years with a mean of 45.8. Household size of 1-8 persons per family (77.8%), acquired secondary school level of education (19.5%), post-secondary education (11.6%), primary education (31.1%), and Qur'anic education (37.7%). Majority (78.1%) have a farm size of 1-2 hectares, with a farming experience of 1- 9 years (92.6%). Farming was their Primary occupation (80.7%). The Majority were crop farmers (74.0%), livestock farmers (14.3%) while (11.7%) practice both crops and livestock production. The result

further revealed that (84.6%) were members of farmer's organizations. Major sources of information on Agricultural credit guarantee scheme loan were Radio/TV programme (30.8%), BSADP-Extension workers (32.1%), CBN /Other banks (17.3%). Major constraints identified in the study were, delay in disbursement of loan (40.7%) low access to information (22.3%), lack of collateral security (19.7%) and also administrative / interest charges accounted for (17.3%). It is therefore recommended that Central Bank of Nigeria and the Bauchi State Agricultural Development Program should increase the awareness level of the loan to farmers. Disbursement should be timely and use of surety should be adopted instead of collateral security like land and buildings. More banks should participate in the scheme to cover more farmers in the state.

Keywords: Analysis, socioeconomic characteristics, agricultural credit guarantee scheme and Bauchi State

INTRODUCTION

Finance plays an important role in agricultural development, and having access to credit facilities for farming purposes is an incentive for increasing the agricultural sector's performance. It is important that financial resources be made available to farmers in order for them to contribute to agricultural development. To this end the central Bank of Nigeria and the federal government initiate the scheme of the Agricultural Credit guarantee Scheme (CBN, 2016). The scheme was introduced to enable farmers exploit the untapped

potentials of Nigeria's agricultural sector. It was established by Decree No. 20 of 1977, and started operations in April, 1978. The Federal Government holds 60% and the Central Bank of Nigeria, 40% of the shares. The aim of the scheme was to enable farmers exploit the untapped potentials of Nigeria's agricultural sector, lower the cost of agricultural production and diversify the economy revenue base (CBN, 2010). The purpose of the Fund is to increase the level of bank credit to the agricultural sector through the provision of guarantee in

respect of loans granted by commercial banks for agricultural purposes. The Agricultural purposes in respect of which loans can be guaranteed by the fund are those connected with:- (a) establishment or management of plantation for the production of rubber, oil palm, cocoa, coffee, tea and similar crops; (b) The production of cereal crops, tubers, fruits of all kinds, cotton, beans, groundnuts, sheanuts, beniseed, vegetables, pine-apples, bananas and plantains; (c) Animal husbandry (poultry, piggery, cattle rearing) fish farming and fish capture; (d) Processing in general where it is integrated with a least 50% of farm output e.g. cassava to gari, oil palm fruit to oil and kernel and groundnut to groundnut oil, (e) Farm machinery and hire services (CBN, 2016). This however, does not apply to loans obtained by state governments for lending. The Central Bank of Nigeria selects through a competitive process, the banks that will participate in the scheme with adequate considerations for the bank's capacity, assets, branch network, liquidity, experience in agricultural lending and credit risk exposures and the banks bear the credit risk of the loans (Agnat, 2004). While the federal government, through the commercial banks puts in place enabling environment for making credit facilities available to farmers with the aim of boosting agricultural production, the utilization of such credit by the farmers depend on myriad of factors. For instance, the perception of the facility by farmers goes a long way in determining the utilization of the facility by farmers. This is mainly informed by the level of education and cultural factors prevalent among farmers, especially in developing countries. Owing to low level of education, most farmers may not have good knowledge of investment and this could lead to poor utilization. Culture could also be a serious hindrance to uptake of loans among certain farmer groups (Enenche *et al.*, 2014). However, thirty-eight years after the introduction of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme in Nigeria there is dearth of information on the socio-economic characteristics of credit beneficiaries under the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme in Bauchi State. Hence, an independent assessment of the socio-economic characteristics of farmers who are credit beneficiaries under the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme would help to provide an insight to socioeconomic characterization of beneficiary farmers under the scheme, identify enterprise type, sources of information and constraints to accessing the credit under the scheme in the study area. In specific terms, this study will form basis of the data the researchers on this area of study will use.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

The study was conducted in Bauchi State. Bauchi State is one of the 36 States that constitute the Nigerian

federation. It is located in the north eastern region of the country and occupies a total land area of 49,119 km² representing about 5.3% of the Nigerian Total land Area. It lies between 10°30'N and 10°50'N of the Equator and 10°10'E. and 10° 10.50'E of the Greenwich Meridian. (Yilkat, 2009). According to census 2006, it has population of 4,676 465 people. The State is characterized by two distinct vegetative zones which include Northern Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah. The study area is bounded by Gombe State to the east, Yobe State to the northeast and Jigawa State to the north. The state also shares border with Kano State to the northwest, Kaduna State to the west while Plateau and Taraba States lie to the south of the State (BSADP, 2010). Bauchi state experienced both wet and dry seasons with the wet season starting from May through October while the dry season sets in, in November. The state is also characterized with an average annual rainfall of 85.6 mm. The main occupation of majority of the indigenes in the area is farming. Pastoralism is practiced mostly by the nomads. Crop farming is ranked highest and this enhanced the designation of the area as agrarian State. Agricultural in the study area is dominated by subsistent farming, practiced by small-scale farmers. Such farmers are largely cash-trapped. They are also generally of low level of education.

Sampling procedure and sample size

Bauchi State has (20) Local Government Areas which are grouped in to three agricultural zones, namely, Northern Zone (9 LGAs) Central Zone (4 LGAs) and Western Zone (7 LGAs). Multi - stage sampling procedure was employed for the selection of respondents for this study. In the first stage, four (4) Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from northern zone, three (3) Local government areas from Western zone and two (2) Local government areas from Central zone, making a total of (9) LGAs. In the second stage, three communities were selected at random from each of the (9) LGAs totaling (27) communities. This was informed by the fact that the numbers of communities in all the Local Government Areas are fairly the same. At the fourth stage, random selection of fifteen (15) respondents from each of the (27) selected communities. These respondents were selected from the list of beneficiaries of credit under the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme. Records of ACGS beneficiaries were obtained from the various financial institutions saddled with the administration of the ACGS from the three zones and the CBN Bauchi Branch. Thus, the total sample size of the respondents for this study was (405) Agricultural credit guarantee scheme beneficiaries.

Data collection and data analysis

The study utilized both primary and secondary of data.

Primary data was collected directly from the respondents through the use of structured questionnaires in line with the objectives of the study while Secondary data were obtained from CBN, Bauchi State Office and other financial institutions that are involved in the administration of the ACGS Loan to farmers in the state. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistical techniques were used to categorize respondents based on socio-economic characteristics, as used by Ajibefun, (2006); Ouma *et al.* (2006); Onu, (2006); Akinola *et al.* (2010); Mignouna *et al.* (2013); Ndaghu *et al.* (2015) and Garba, (2017). Also, regression analysis was used to analyze farmers' decision to collect loan as well as the amount of loan collected was used as the dependent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Studies on the impact of agricultural credit and credit guarantee scheme to assist farmers increase food production for national food security are needed to help improve the flow of credit to the agricultural sector and improve the operations of guarantee schemes. Empirical studies have emphasized the importance of socio-economic factors in influencing the decision of farmers on the need to borrow credit for agricultural finance or not. The socio-economic characteristics of respondents considered in this study include: age, sex, marital status, house hold size, education, source of farm land, farm size, farming experience, primary occupation and membership of farmer organization (Olagunju and Adeyemo, 2007; Kehinde, 2012; Enenche *et al.*, 2014).

Age of the respondents

Age refers to the number of years that a respondent had lived since birth to the time of the study. Age is an important variable factor to influencing the decision of a farmer to borrow credit for financing agricultural activities. Younger farmers are full of energy and aspirations needed for driving production to optimum level while older farmers are full of experiences and technical know-how of the production techniques hence both the two are essentials (Malimbwi *et al.*, 2009; Enenche *et al.*, 2014; Garba, 2017). The result shows that 45.8% of the respondents were within the age bracket of 20 to 45 years. Only small proportions (8.6%) of the respondents were above 55 years of age. The mean age among the respondents was 45.8 years. This implies that access to Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme is not in the hands of too old people. The farmers are still very active and should be highly productive if they have access to adequate productivity enhancing inputs at the right time.

Sex of the respondents

Sex refers to category of the respondents either male or female. Results show the distribution of the respondents according to sex. The result revealed the dominance of male farmers (73.8%) in the study area. Female farmers constituted only about one-quarter (27.8%) of the respondents. This result is an indication that access to credit by females is still low despite their active participation in agriculture. Fletschner and Kenney, (2011) noted that many women's access to financial services is mediated through their husbands and yet if they had direct access, it would lead to higher investment in human capital, which would have long term impact on child health, nutrition and education.

Marital status of the respondents

Marital status in the context of this study refers to the respondent been married or single. Results on marital status of the respondents revealed that majority (76.5%) of the respondents were married. Only small fractions 13.0% and 10.4% of the respondents were single and divorced respectively. This implies that majority of farmers who access credit from the scheme are married, thus suggesting that confers some degree of responsibility that stimulate farmers to seek means for meeting their responsibilities. Garba, (2017) reported that marital status of the respondents stimulate them to find additional means of income to take care of the enormous family responsibilities, such as payment of children school fees, settling family medical bills, and many more. Additional means of income generation could be through increase in farm output and income.

Level of education of the respondents

Level of education refers to acquisition of knowledge through formal or organized means or through schooling. In this study education was measured as the number of years the respondent has engaged in formal schooling. Education makes it possible for people to share and use information and equally make sound decision with respect to Agricultural lending. For rural people, education equips them with the ability to take advantage of developmental programmes such as the ones in agriculture. The relevance of education to agricultural development programmes could be seen in the opportunities that are opened to the educated farmer to read and understand extension bulletins, posters and understand all the procedures of accessing loan facilities and loan repayment agreement terms. Education is among the most important determinants of participation in development issues. It creates a favorable condition for communication and dissemination of improved technologies in agriculture. The result clearly shows that

37.7% of the total respondents had Qur'anic education, 31.1% had attended primary level of education and 19.5% attained secondary level of education. Also 11.6% were exposed to post secondary level of education. This results is in agreement with the findings of Chen and Chiivakul, (2008); Bendig *et al.*, (2009); Tang *et al.*, (2010); Garba, (2017).

Household size of the respondents

Household size refers to the total number of people in the household which includes the wives, children and dependents who reside within the family and eat from the "same pot". Garba, (2017) opined that household size is considered as the number of people living together under the same roof. Size of household was measured as the total number of people living within the family at the time of this study. The result shows that 42.5% of the respondents had 5 to 8 members in their household and 35.3% of the respondents had 1 to 4 members per household. Only 18.5% of the respondents had 9 to 12 members in their household. In addition, 3.7% had a household size of 13 and above members in their household. Household size determines the available human labor force leaving together and eating from the same pot that can be employed in carrying out agricultural activities. Household size determines the availability of household labour supply (Agwu, 2004; Amos, 2007; Idrisa, 2009; Mignouna *et al.*, 2013; Ndaghu *et al.*, 2015; Garba, 2017). The subsistence nature of the farmers does not leave them with enough capital to re-invest in their farming activities and the need for labor is higher especially during weeding and harvesting. This informed the need for labor from family source. Hence, the capacity of households to pay hired labour cannot be overemphasized. The implication here is that cost of production is less by the abundance of available family labour. More hands are available to attend to all aspects of the farm operations.

Total farm size and source of land of the respondents

Farm size refers to the totality of the farm lands the respondents owned plus rented during the study period. The result of the study reveals that about half (52.5%) of the respondents had less than 1 hectare of farm land while 25.6% of the respondents had between 1 – 2 hectares of farm land, also 9.8% of the respondents had a total farm size of 3 – 4 hectares with only 11.8% of the respondents having a total farm land of 5 hectares and above. This result agrees with Agwu, *et al.*, (2008) reported that Nigerian farmers are generally small scale farmers that cultivated small areas of land. The relatively small farm size of the respondents will inevitably lead to subsistence farming which do not encourage commercial

farming. This implies that the study area comprises mainly small scale farmers. Table 1 revealed the sources of farm land of the respondents. The result shows that 32.0% of the respondents obtained their land through inheritance, 20.4% of the respondents obtained their land through purchase while 11.6% of the respondents used communal land. The result also revealed that 11.1% of the respondents obtained the land through hire/rented. This result is in agreement with the finding of Garba, (2017) they all reported that most of their respondents obtained their farm land through inheritance. This indicates that majority of the respondents had access to permanent land for the production since they are owners of the land compared with a tenant that can be ejected at will by the land owner. The other means of acquiring a farm land by the respondents is through purchase and hire. These show that there is available land for agricultural activities that farmer can access.

Primary occupation of the respondents

Primary occupation means the basic source for which the respondents earn his/her living other than any other secondary sources if available. This result revealed that majority (80.7%) of the respondents was full time farmers while 19.2% were engaged in non agricultural activities as their primary occupation. Garba, (2017) reported that majority of the farmers who apply for credit in Jigawa state spent most of their time working on farm. It also suggests that being highly dependent on farming they may be willingly to borrow more money for the purchase of the needful agricultural inputs including tools and machinery at the early stage. It is generally believed that people who take farming as their secondary occupation or as a hobby do not have keen interest to go for credit in order to increase production compared to farmers who take farming as their primary occupation, Ado, (2012). This implies that any government intervention programme that involves giving loan or credit to rural farmers should first target full time farmers since they are the majority.

Years of farming experience

Garba, (2017) farming Experience refers to the length of time taken in years that the respondent had been engaged in farming as an occupation. The practical experience of a farmer counts a lot in his ability to collect loan or not to collect.

Farming experience was measured as the actual number of years since a respondent started farming generally as an occupation. Result showed that about half (52.0%) of the respondents had 4-6 years farming experience, while 27.1% of the respondents had 7-9 years of farming experience, also, 13.5% of the respondents had 1-3 years of farming experience while

Table 1. Distribution of respondents based on socio-economic characteristics.

Socio-economic variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
20 – 35	70	17.3
36 – 45	115	28.4
46 – 55	140	34.6
56 – 65	45	11.1
66 and above	35	8.6
Total	405	100
Sex		
Male	299	73.8
Female	106	26.2
Total	405	100
Marital status		
Married	310	76.5
Single	53	13.0
Widow/divorcee	42	10.4
Total	405	100
Household size		
1-4	143	35.3
5-8	172	42.5
9-12	75	18.5
13-16	10	2.5
17 above	05	1.2
Total	405	100
Educational qualification		
Post secondary education	47	11.6
Qur'anic education	153	37.7
Primary education	126	31.1
Secondary education	79	19.5
Total	405	100
Primary occupation		
Farming	327	80.7
Others	78	19.2
Total	405	100
Farm size (ha)		
< 1ha	213	52.5
1-2	104	25.6
3-4	40	9.8
5 and above	48	11.8
Total	405	100
Source of land		
Inheritance	130	32.0
Purchase	83	20.4
Hired/rented	45	11.1
Communal	47	11.6
Total	405	100
Membership of farmer organization		
Member	343	84.6
Non member	62	15.4
Total	405	100
Years of farming experience		
1-3 Year	55	13.5
4-6 Years	211	52.0
7-9 Years	110	27.1
10 and above Years	29	7.1
Total	405	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

Table 2. Distribution of respondents based on type of farming enterprises.

Farming enterprises	Frequency	Percentage
Crop production	300	74.0
Livestock production	58	14.3
Both crop and livestock production	47	11.7
Total	405	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

Table 3. Distributions of respondents sources of information on ACGS loan.

Sources of information	Frequency	Percentage
Radio/TV programme	125	30.8
ADP Extension agents	130	32.1
CBN (visits and sensitization)	70	17.3
Friends/ neighbors	80	19.8
Total	405	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

Table 4. Major constraints to accessing ACGSF loan in Bauchi State.

Constraints	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Lack of collateral security	96	23.7	1 st
Low information about ACGSF	55	13.5	2 nd
Low number of participating banks	75	18.5	3 rd
Delay in disbursement of loan	74	18.2	4 th
Interest rate is high and unaffordable	65	16.0	5 th
Cost of processing ACGSF loan is high	40	9.8	6 th
Total	405	100	

Source: Field survey, 2018

7.1% had farming experience for more than 10 years. This result is similar with the findings of Sabo, (2005) and Ado, (2012).

Membership of farmer's organizations

Idrisa, (2009), opined that membership of farmer organization refers to the level of social participation of the respondents in farmer's cooperatives societies and organizations which positively influences farmers' decision to get credit from financial institutions. The results showed that majority (84.6%) of the respondents were members of one farmer's organizations or another. Only 15.4% of the respondents were not members to any farmers' organization, Garba, (2017). Membership of farmer's organization has a positive bearing on the capacity of farmers to collect loan and utilize it well. For instance, farmers' cooperative organizations link members to source(s) of inputs, credits, educate their members on how to utilize such inputs as well as link them to markets where they can dispose their produce.

Farming enterprises of the respondents

This involves the type of farming practices that the

farmers engaged themselves such as crop or livestock farming and those that practice both crop and livestock production. The result in (Table 2) revealed that majority 74.0% of the respondents were crop producers, and 14.3% were livestock farmers only while 11.7% practiced both (crops and livestock production). Yilkat (2009) and Apantaku *et al.* (2005) reported that majority of farmers in Bauchi (74%) and Ogun (96%) states practiced both crop and livestock production.

Sources of information on ACGS loan to the respondents

ACGS beneficiaries' sources to information refer to the means or channels on how they hear or get the information about the ACGS loan. Farmers rely on variety of information sources to lead them from the awareness stage to the acceptance and/or rejection stage. The result in (Table 3) revealed that 30.8% of the respondents received information about ACGS loan through radio/TV programs, 32.1% of the total respondents got the information from the State Agricultural Development Project (ADP) extension agents, and 19.8% got the information from neighbors/friends, and still 17.3% got the information from the central bank of Nigeria through sensitization and visits. This result agrees with the findings

of Ado, (2012) who reported in his study on assessment of JARDA in promoting agriculture in Jigawa State, Nigeria, that 50% of the respondents rated radio as the most accessible means of their awareness with agricultural information. Another study conducted by Adejo, (2007) on access of rural farmers to information and communication technologies for the development of agriculture in Bauchi State, Nigeria, revealed that 81.00% of the farmers possessed radio sets. Garba (2006) reported 50.8% and 22.5% of the farmers in Bauchi LGA sourced their information from radio programmes and village extension agents respectively.

Constraints in accessing loans from ACGSF in Bauchi State

The result in Table 4 shows the major constraints to access ACGSF loan in Bauchi state: lack of collateral security (23.7%) and ranked 1st. Furthermore, low access to information about ACGSF (18.5%) 2nd Low number of participating banks (18.2%) 3rd The result also shows that delay in disbursement of loan (13.5%) 4th, is another important constraint to access to ACGSF loan. Interest rate is high and unaffordable (16.0%) 5th while cost of processing ACGSF loan is high (9.8%) 6th. This corroborate with Enenche *et al.* (2014) who mentioned that, the time lag between application and disbursement of credit service was indicated as the major constraints borrowers faced. This implies that delay in approval/disbursement of credit and lack of collateral security constituted the major constraints to sourcing agricultural credit among the respondents. These probably explain why most farmers prefer to patronize the non-formal financial sector. This result is similar with the result of Okojie *et al.* (2010), the lack of bank accounts, collateral, and information regarding the procedure for accessing credits from banks limits rural women's access to credit from formal institutions. Adejobi and Atobatele, (2008) suggested that loan default could limit access to credit, while Agnet, (2004) opined that the complex mechanism of commercial banking is least understood by the small-scale farmers, and thus, limits their access. Rahji and Fakayode, (2009) blamed the limitation on imperfect and costly information problems encountered in the financial markets; credit rationing policy; and banks' perception of agricultural credit as a highly risky venture; while Philip *et al.* (2009) stated that high interest rate and the short-term nature of loans with fixed repayment periods do not suit annual cropping, and thus constitute a hindrance to credit access. An interview with the ACGS Fund desk of the SME Unit of CBN suggested that small-scale farmers' low access to credit institutions is due to the requirement for collateral and the perceived high risk and uncertainty of agricultural production. An interview with a cooperative official corroborated the notion that unstable markets tied to uncertain harvests increased

lenders' perceptions of risk in lending to small-scale farmers. Other interviews suggested that credit is misallocated to non intended beneficiaries in government-backed credit programs.

Conclusion and recommendations

The findings from this study showed that small-scale crop farmers dominate the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund loan in Bauchi State. Nevertheless, household size determines the availability of labour supply. Extension agents and radio were the major sources of information to Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund loan beneficiaries in the study area. However, collateral security, low number of participating bank and sources of information about the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund loan were the major constraints. The result of this study is expected to give direction to policy makers of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme. It is therefore recommended that Central Bank of Nigeria and the Bauchi State Agricultural Development Program should increase the awareness level of the loan to farmers. Disbursement should be timely and use of surety should be adopted instead of collateral security like land and buildings. More banks should participate in the scheme to cover more farmers in the state.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research that was carried out by our research team and we agreed to publish it in the journal.

REFERENCES

- Adejo PE (2007). *Access of Rural Farmers to Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of Agriculture in Bauchi L.G.A , Bauchi State, Nigeria*. Unpublished M.sc thesis, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi.
- Adejobi O, Atobatele JT (2008). An analysis of loan delinquency among small-scale farmers in southwestern Nigeria: Application of logit and loan performance indices. *East African Agricultural and Forestry Journal* 74 (3).
- Ado G (2012). Assessment of Jigawa Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (JARDA) in promoting agriculture in Jigawa State, Nigeria. *Biological and Environmental Sciences Journal for the Tropics*, 2. 38-41.
- Agnet (2004). Making Farm Credit Work for the Small Scale farmers (www.agnet.org/library)
- Agwu EA (2004). Factors Influencing Adoption of Improved Cowpea Production Technologies in Nigeria. Retrieved December, 2015 from http://www.aiaee.org/attachments/195_Agwu-Vol-11.1-9.pdf.
- Agwu AE, Ekueme JN Anyanwu AC (2008). "Adoption of improved agricultural technologies disseminated via radio programme by farmers in Enugu State Nigeria", *African Journal of Biotechnology* 7(9): 1277-1286.
- Ajibefun IA (2006). Linking socio-economic and policy variables to technical efficiency of traditional Agricultural production: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. Paper presented at International Association of Agricultural Economists' Conference, Gold Coast, Australia, August.

- Akinola AA, Alene AD, Adeyemo R Sanogo D, Olanrewaju AS, Nwoke C, Nziguheba G (2010). Determinants of adoption and intensity of use of balance nutrient management systems technologies in the northern Guinea savanna of Nigeria. *Quarterly Journal of International Agriculture* 9 (1): 25-45.
- Amos TT (2007). An analysis of productivity and technical efficiency of smallholder cocoa farmers in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*. 15(2):127-133.
- Apantaku SO, Awotunde JM, Adegbite D A, Ajayi EA (2005): Feasibility of Private Integrated Agricultural Extension Services in Ogun state Nigeria: *Journal of Agricultural Extension* 5(8): 150-154.
- Bauchi State Agricultural Development Programme (2010). Western Zone Crop Area Yields Surveys. Bauchi State Agricultural Report. p.12.
- CBN (2010). *Statistical Bulletin*. Abuja Central Bank of Nigeria.
- CBN (2016). *Annual Report and Statement of Account*. Abuja, Nigeria.
- Chen KC, Chiivakul M (2008). What Drives Household Borrowing and Credit Constraints? Evidence from Bosnia and Herzegovina. *New York*.
- Enenche EA, Ohen SB, Umeze GE (2014). The Effect of Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) on Production Efficiency of Rural Farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research: D Agriculture and Veterinary*. 14 (10): 309 – 310.
- Flitschner D, Kenney L (2011). Rural women's access to financial services: credit, savings and insurance. *ESA Working Paper No. 11-07 March 2011*. Agricultural Development Economics Division. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/economic/esa>
- Garba A (2006). *Analysis of factors influencing adoption of SG, 2000 maize production technology in Bauchi state, Nigeria*. Unpublished M.Sc thesis Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Nigeria.
- Garba A (2017). *Analysis of the determinants of adoption of improved sesame seed technology among small-scale farmers in jigawa state, Nigeria*. Unpublished Ph.D thesis Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Nigeria.
- Idrisa YL (2009). *Analysis of determinants of adoption of improved soybean seed technology among farmers in southern Borno State, Nigeria*. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.
- Kehinde AA (2012). Agricultural Financing in Nigeria: An Assessment of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) For Food Security in Nigeria (1978-2006).
- Malimbwi R, E,Katani JZ, Zahabu E, Mugasha WA (2009). *Improving Small holder livelihoods through woodlots management. An adaptation to climate variability and change in makele district Tanzania*. A research proposal, sokoine, university of agriculture, morogoro, Tanzaninya.
- Mignouna BD, Abdoulaye T, Kamara A, Oluoch M (2013). Baseline study of smallholder farmers in *Striga*-infested maize and cowpea-growing areas of northern Nigeria. *International Institute for Tropical Agriculture*, Ibadan, Nigeria.p. 60.
- Ndaghu NN, Zakari A, Shehu A Tahirou A (2015). Socio-economic factors affecting adoption of early maturing maize varieties by small scale farmers in Safana Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*. 5(6):562-567.
- Okojie C, Monye-Emina A, Eghafona K, Osaghae G, Ehiakhamen JO (2010). Institutional environment and access to microfinance by self-employed women in the rural areas of Edo State. NSSP Brief No. 14. Washington. D.C. International Food Policy Research Institute.
- Olagunju FI, Ajiboye A (2010). Agricultural Lending Decision: A Tobit Regression Analysis. *Afr. J. Food Agric. Nutr. Dev.*, 10 (5): 116-118.
- Onu DO (2006). Socio-economic Factors Influencing Farmers' Adoption of Alley Farming Technology Under Intensified Agriculture in Imo State, Nigeria. *The Philippine Agricultural Scientist Journal*. 8(2):45-52.
- Ouma JO, Hugo DG, George O (2006). Determinants of Improved Maize Seed and Fertilizer use In Kenya: Policy Implications. Contributed paper presented at the International Association of Agricultural Economists Conference, Gold Coast, Australia, Pp.12-18.
- Philip D, Nkonya E, Pender J, Oni OA (2009). Constraints to Increasing Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria. A review. Nigeria Strategy Support Program (NSSP) Background Paper No. 006.
- Rahji MAY, Fakayode SA (2009). A Multinomial Logit analysis of Agricultural Credit Rationing by Commercial Banks in Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics* 24:91.
- Sabo UU (2005). Impact of Participatory Extension Activities on Sesame Production in Ringim and Taura Local Government Areas of Jigawa State. A Thesis Submitted to the Post-graduate School, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Sociology, Faculty of Agriculture Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.
- Yilkat YY (2009). The role of Agricultural Extension in controlling soil Erosion in Bauchi state. *Unpublished M.sc thesis, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi*.